
ASSESSMENT OF SATISFACTION WITH MEDICINE INFORMATION AMONG
PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC DISEASES AT A NIGERIAN TERTIARY
HEALTHCARE FACILITY

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Abstract

Background: Medicine information is a critical component of pharmaceutical care for patients on chronic medication therapy. This pharmacist led service is expected to provide basic information on the purpose, usage, storage and benefits of therapy as well as potential side effects of medicines. The information is expected to be patient specific and tailored to meet unique needs at various stages of medication therapy. Satisfaction with medicine information is known to improve clinical outcomes, reduce adverse drug events and help patients achieve better adherence with medications among other benefits. In recent times there are concerns about the quality of medicine information provided to patients and its effects on satisfaction with pharmaceutical care service experience in public health facilities in the country. This study therefore aim to explore patients satisfaction with information received alongside their dispensed medications.

Methods: This was a cross sectional survey study carried out among patients with four common non-communicable diseases. A total of four hundred and twelve respondents selected using convenience sampling were self-administered with “satisfaction with information about medicine scale” (SIMS). The seventeen item four point Likert scale instrument (Too much, about okay, too little, non-received and non-needed) was scored as satisfied (about right and non-needed scored = 1) and other options were classified as unsatisfied (score = 0). Satisfaction was determined using summary score of > 12 and further analysis was done using Students t test, one way ANOVA and Chi square test. P values <0.05 was significant.

Results: Satisfaction with medicine information ranged between 13.8 to 44.5% of patients with the highest being “how to get a further supply” (44.5%) and the least “what to do if you forget to take a dose” (13.8%). There are significant differences in satisfaction between different aspects of medicine information and demographic variables ($p < 0.001$). Satisfaction is significantly associated with gender ($p < 0.001$), marital status ($p < 0.001$), educational level ($p = 0.009$) and duration of therapy ($p = 0.003$).

Conclusion: Satisfaction with medicine information was generally low and an indication of ineffective information service delivery system. There is need to revise the current medicine information service delivery to not only improve satisfaction but also to promote proper use of medicines among patients on chronic disease medication therapy.

Keywords: Medicine information, chronic diseases, satisfaction, pharmaceutical care

Introduction

Medication information is a central component of pharmaceutical care services that should be provided to all patients particularly to those on complex

medication therapy for non-communicable diseases. The four commonly encountered non-communicable diseases include hypertension, diabetes, asthma and cancers

require lifelong medication therapy (Idris *et al*, 2020, Wang & Wang, 2020) and patients are expected to be active participants in long term medical care (Devi *et al*, 2020, Lorber *et al*, 2020). It is therefore of critical importance for patients to be provided with adequate medication information needed for effective participation in treatment planning, adherence and optimization of clinical outcomes (Geryk *et al*, 2016, Nafradi *et al*, 2016).

Medicines play a central role in the treatment of non-communicable diseases as well as prevention of long term complications. Recent studies have exposed major gaps between information needs of patients and that provided by healthcare providers (Chan *et al*, 2020, Boons *et al*, 2018). Furthermore, there is increasing awareness that long term medication therapy is challenged by side effects, non-adherence, confusion from complex treatment regimens, multiple dosing schedules, proper storage of medicines, drug interactions with food, alcohol and other drugs (Sheik *et al*, 2017). These problems cannot be effectively prevented or ameliorated without active participation of patients through adequate counseling and medication information (Alshahrani, 2023).

In typical hospital settings, verbal and written medicine information is usually provided during the dispensing process, however problems remain with patient misunderstanding of instructions, ability to read, recall of oral information, wrong application of instructions and mix up of important details required for proper use of medications etc. (Benson *et al*, 2021, Niriayo *et al*, 2018). In addition the need for medicine information frequently change over time due to changes in drug regimen, emergence of complications and adverse drug events all of which require regular revision of information that is needed by

patients (Eibergen *et al*, 2018). This evolution of information needs and the inability of providers to keep up with the pace of changes is a significant source of dissatisfaction (Kusch *et al*, 2018).

The provision of adequate medication information is important for the prevention of medication errors (Sheik *et al*, 2017, Donaldson *et al*, 2017), potentially harmful interactions and avoidable adverse events (Takaki *et al*, 2017, Rameshkumar *et al*, 2022). The benefits of adequate medicine information extends well beyond direct clinical outcomes (Walker *et al*, 2023, Aldarwesh *et al*, 2022, Undeberg *et al*, 2022) to include improved adherence (Unni *et al*, 2022, Makhinova *et al*, 2022), enhance knowledge of disease (Sze *et al*, 2020), reduction in side effects (Langst *et al*, 2015) and safer use of drugs (Jose, 2020).

Satisfaction with medication information is however known to be influenced by presentation format (Wongtaweepekij *et al*, 2021, Johnson *et al*, 2003), cultural and language barriers (Nguyen *et al*, 2019), trust (Sulistyaningrum *et al*, 2023, Druica *et al*, 2021), disease type (Adeniyi *et al*, 2017) and level of health literacy (Aggarwal *et al*, 2024, Martin, 2019). While the role of medication information in patient participation in treatment decisions is not in dispute (Sertan *et al*, 2023), its quality have been of mix performance (Chan *et al*, 2020).

The poor information delivery system in sub Saharan countries have frequently produced inconsistent findings, although most of them have reported poor satisfaction among patients (Lucca *et al*, 2022, Ade *et al*, 2020) while others reported moderate level of satisfaction (Hammar & Zetterholm, 2020, Ofili *et al*, 2023). Medication information should be part of routine pharmaceutical care provided to patients, so assessment offers an

opportunity to view its quality from the perspective of patient's service experience. This study therefore aim to evaluate satisfaction with the quality of medicine information among patients being managed with selected non-communicable diseases and its association with demographic factors.

Methods

Settings: The study was carried out among outpatients living with four chronic diseases (Diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension (HTN), cardiovascular diseases (CVD) and asthma) in a tertiary care hospital.

Study design: This was a cross sectional survey study carried out among patients being managed in the hospital.

Sample size/sampling: The sample size was determined using Raosoft calculator at 95% confidence interval and 5% margin of error. The sample size was 377 and 10% attrition rate factored in bring the final sample size to 415. The respondents were selected using simple random sampling method.

Eligibility criteria:

- Patients being managed for DM2, HTN, asthma or CHF
- Patients must have being on therapy for at least six months
- Patients with coexisting non-communicable disease were excluded

Questionnaire: Satisfaction with information about medicine scale (Horne *et al*, 2001) consist of 17 items relating medicine knowledge and use. Each item was rated on a four point Likert scale (*Too much, about okay, too little, non-received and non-needed*) and patients were required to rate information they were provided

about their current medications. While “*about right*” and “*non-needed*” were classified as satisfied (*score = 1*), other options were classified as unsatisfied (*score = 0*). Item scores ranged from 0 to 17 with scores (> 12) indicating satisfaction while scores of ≤ 12 is dissatisfaction.

Data collection: The questionnaire was self-administered on patients who provided verbal consent and after receiving their medicines at the pharmacy department of the hospital. A total of 430 questionnaires were administered out of which 412 were used for final analysis giving a return rate of 93%.

Data analysis: The data were entered into Microsoft excel, cleaned and loaded into SPSS version 21 for descriptive and inferential analysis. Student's t test, one way ANOVA and Chi square were used to determine significant differences and /or association between demographic variables and satisfaction with medicine information. P values < 0.05 was statistically significant.

Ethical issues: Approval for the study was obtained from the health research ethics committee of the Borno State specialist hospital Maiduguri (SSH/GEN/641/Vol.1).

Result

Demographic data showed that 54.2% of respondents were males compared to 45.8% females. Majority of respondents were married (85.5%) and major occupations were civil service (49.7%) and self-employment (38.5%). About half of respondents had secondary level education (50%) and tertiary level education was reported by 26.8% of them. The most encountered diseases were CVDs (31%), HTN (25%), DM2 (25.2%) and least being asthma (18.8%). The mean duration of therapy was 4.4 ± 1.4 years (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Demographic data

Variable	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	217	54.2
Female	183	45.8
Age (yrs.)		
≤ 40	92	23
41 – 50	100	25
51 – 60	79	19.8
61 – 70	69	17.2
≥ 71	60	15
Mean age (yrs.) = 49.7 ± 18.6		
Marital status		
Single	13	3.3
Married	342	85.5
Widowed	45	11.2
Occupation		
Civil servant	199	49.7
Self employed	154	38.5
Unemployed	47	11.8
Farming		
Educational status		
Primary	93	23.2
Secondary	200	50
Tertiary	107	26.8
Morbidity		
DM2	101	25.2
HTN	100	31
Asthma	75	18.8
CVD	124	25
Duration of therapy (yrs.)		
<2	36	9
2 – 5	147	36.8
> 5	217	54.2
Mean duration (yrs.) = 4.4 ± 1.4		

Key: DM2 – diabetes mellitus type 2, HTN – hypertension, CVD – cardiovascular diseases

Satisfaction with medicine information on items ranged from 13.8 to 44.5% with “*how to get a further supply*” (44.5%), “*how to use your medicine*” (43.5%) and “*what is the name of your medicine called*” (35.3%) being the highest levels. Satisfaction with “*what to do if you forget to take a dose*” (13.8%) was the least (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Satisfaction with medicine information

The distribution of item response to items showed overall satisfaction with medicine information of 38.7% among respondents. The level of dissatisfaction was highest with “*what to do if a dose is missed*” (86.2%) and “*what medicines do*” (85.5%) as well as “*how medicines work*” (84.2%) (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Distribution of response to items

Item description		Too much N (%)	About right N (%)	Too little N (%)	Non received N (%)	Non needed N (%)
Q1	What is the name of your medicine called	231 (57.7)	141 (35.3)	28 (7.0)	-	-
Q2	What is your medicine for	227 (56.7)	70 (17.5)	36 (9.0)	67 (16.8)	-
Q3	What your medicine do	172 (43)	30 (7.5)	142 (35.5)	28 (7.0)	28(7.0)
Q4	How your medicine works	113 (28.2)	50 (12.5)	149 (37.3)	64 (16)	24 (6)
Q5	How long it takes to act	115 (28.7)	59 (14.8)	180 (45)	16 (4)	30 (7.5)
Q6	How can you tell if it is working	51 (12.8)	62 (15.5)	148 (37)	64 (16)	75(18.7)
Q7	How long will you need to be on your medicine	141 (35.3)	70 (17.5)	85 (21.2)	80 (20)	24 (6)
Q8	How to use your medicine	100 (25)	112 (28)	59 (14.7)	67 (16.8)	62 (15.5)
Q9	How to get a further supply	103 (25.8)	129 (32.2)	110 (27.5)	28 (7)	30 (7.5)
Q10	Whether the medicine has any unwanted side effects	56 (14)	99 (24.7)	105 (26.3)	108 (27)	32 (8)
Q11	What are the risks of you getting side effects	84 (21)	81 (20.3)	142 (35.5)	61 (15.2)	32 (8)
Q12	What to do if you experience unwanted side effects	79 (19.8)	64 (16)	139 (34.7)	81 (20.3)	37 (9.2)
Q13	Whether you can drink alcohol while on this medicine	35 (8.7)	92 (23)	87 (21.8)	138 (34.5)	48 (12)
Q14	Whether this medicine interfere with other medicines	12 (3)	55 (13.7)	141 (35.3)	140 (35)	52 (13)
Q15	Whether this medicine will make you drowsy	77 (19.3)	70 (17.5)	128 (32)	99 (24.7)	26 (6.5)
Q16	Whether this medicine will affect your sex life	51 (12.8)	82 (20.5)	118 (29.5)	95 (23.7)	54 (13.5)
Q17	What you should do if you forget to take a dose	87 (21.7)	34 (8.5)	137 (34.3)	121 (30.2)	21 (5.3)

Key: “About right” and “non-needed” were scored as satisfaction items

Satisfaction with information on “*what name is your medicine*” and “*what your medicine do*” were associated with age, morbidity, educational status and duration of therapy (P<0.001). While “*what is your medicine for*” was associated with age (P<0.001), education (P<0.001), morbidity (P = 0.016) and duration of therapy (P = 0.020). “*How your medicine work*” is associated with all the demographic variables except age (P = 0.988) and gender (P = 0.460) (**Table 3**).

Table 3: Satisfaction with knowledge of medicines

Variable	Q1. What is the name of your medicine			Q2. What is your medicine for			Q3. What your medicine do			Q4. How your medicine work		
	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value
Gender												
Male	83 (38.2)	134 (61.8)	0.172	70 (32.2)	147 (67.8)	0.361	35 (16.1)	182 (83.9)	0.314	37 (17.1)	182 (82.9)	0.460
Female	58 (31.7)	125 (68.3)		67 (36.6)	116 (63.4)		23 (12.6)	160 (87.4)		26 (14.2)	157 (85.8)	
Age (yrs.)												
≤ 40	12 (14.1)	80 (85.9)	<0.001	13 (14.1)	79 (85.9)	<0.001	8 (8.7)	84 (91.3)	0.262	15 (16.3)	77 (83.7)	0.988
41 – 50	39 (39)	61 (61)		40 (40)	60 (60)		18 (18)	82 (82)		14 (14)	86 (86)	
51 – 60	48 (60.7)	31 (39.3)		43 (54.4)	36 (45.6)		15 (18.9)	64 (81.1)		13 (16.4)	66 (83.6)	
61 – 70	22 (31.9)	47 (68.1)		24 (34.8)	45 (65.2)		8 (11.6)	61 (88.4)		11 (15.9)	58 (84.1)	
≥71	20 (33.3)	40 (66.7)		17 (28.3)	43 (71.7)		9 (15)	51 (85)		10 (16.7)	50 (83.3)	
Education												
Primary	27 (29)	66 (71)	<0.001	19 (20.4)	74 (79.6)	<0.001	5 (5.4)	88 (94.6)	<0.001	4 (4.3)	89 (95.7)	<0.001
Secondary	54 (27)	146 (73)		60 (30)	140 (70)		16 (8)	184 (92)		18 (9)	182 (91)	
Tertiary	60 (56.1)	47 (43.9)		58 (54.2)	49 (45.8)		37 (34.6)	69 (65.4)		41 (38.3)	66 (62.7)	
Marital status												

Single	4 (30.8)	9 (69.2)	0.136	7 (53.8)	6 (46.2)	0.317	3 (23.1)	9 (76.9)	0.559	6 (46.1)	7 (53.9)	<0.001
Married	127 (37.1)	215 (62.9)		115 (33.6)	227 (66.4)		48 (14)	294 (86)		48 (14)	294 (86)	
Widowed	10 (22.2)	35 (77.8)		15 (33.3)	30 (66.7)		7 (15.5)	38 (84.5)		9 (20)	36 (64)	
Morbidity												
DM2	22 (21.8)	79 (78.2)	<0.001	37 (36.6)	64 (63.4)	0.016	17 (16.8)	84 (83.2)	<0.001	17 (16.8)	84 (83.2)	0.069
HTN	25 (25)	75 (75)		33 (33)	67 (67)		28 (28)	82 (72)		19 (19)	81 (81)	
Asthma	16 (21.3)	59 (78.7)		15 (20)	60 (80)		9 (12)	66 (88)		16 (21.3)	59 (78.7)	
CVD	78 (62.9)	46 (37.1)		52 (41.9)	72 (58.1)		4 (3.2)	120 (96.8)		11 (8.9)	113 (91.1)	
Duration (yrs.)												
< 2	12 (33.3)	24 (66.7)	<0.001	16 (44.4)	20 (55.6)	0.020	7 (19.4)	29 (80.6)	0.660	9 (25)	27 (75)	0.054
2 - 5	31 (21.1)	116 (78.9)		38 (25.8)	109 (74.2)		20 (13.6)	127 (86.4)		28 (19)	119 (81)	
> 5	98 (45.2)	119 (54.8)		83 (38.2)	134 (61.8)		31 (14.3)	186 (85.7)		26 (11.9)	191 (88.1)	

Key: STF – *satisfied*, NSTF – *not satisfied*

Patients educational status and morbidity had significant association with satisfaction ($P < 0.001$) while other items had mixed results. For instance, age and duration of therapy were associated with “*how long medicine take to work*” ($P < 0.001$) and “*how to tell if your medicine is working*” ($P < 0.001$), gender was only associated with “*how can you tell if your medicine is working*” ($P = 0.002$). Marital status was significantly associated with “*how long medicine take to work*” ($P = 0.001$) and “*how long you will be taking your medicine*” ($P < 0.001$) (**Table 4**).

Table 4: Satisfaction with medicine use information

Variable	Q5. How long medicine takes to work			Q6. How can you tell if your medicine is working			Q7. How long will you be taking your medicine			Q8. How to use your medicine		
	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value
Gender												
Male	61 (28.1)	156 (71.9)	0.515	88 (40.5)	129 (59.5)	0.002	49 (22.6)	168 (72.4)	0.637	98 (45.2)	119 (54.8)	0.465
Female	29 (15.8)	154 (84.2)		49 (26.8)	139 (73.2)		45 (24.6)	138 (75.3)		76 (41.5)	107 (58.5)	
Age (yrs.)												
≤ 40	12 (14.1)	80 (85.9)	<0.001	14 (15.2)	78 (84.8)	<0.001	17 (18.5)	75 (81.5)	0.315	37 (40.2)	55 (59.8)	0.281
41 – 50	21 (21)	79 (79)		32 (32)	68 (68)		19 (19)	81 (81)		39 (49)	51 (51)	
51 – 60	16 (20.2)	63 (79.8)		41 (51.9)	38 (48.1)		22 (27.8)	57 (72.2)		39 (49.3)	40 (50.7)	
61 – 70	30 (43.5)	39 (56.5)		19 (27.5)	50 (72.5)		20 (28.9)	49 (71.1)		22 (31.9)	47 (68.1)	
≥71	11 (18.3)	49 (81.7)		31 (51.7)	29 (48.3)		16 (26.7)	44 (73.3)		27 (45)	33 (55)	
Education												
Primary	10 (10.7)	80 (89.3)	<0.001	17 (18.3)	76 (81.7)	<0.001	14 (15.1)	79 (84.9)	<0.001	23 (24.7)	70 (75.3)	0.001
Secondary	23 (11.5)	177 (88.5)		45 (22.5)	155 (77.5)		36 (18)	164 (82)		94 (47)	106 (53)	
Tertiary	57 (53.3)	50 (46.7)		75 (70.1)	32 (29.9)		44 (41.1)	63 (58.9)		57 (53.3)	50 (46.7)	
Marital status												
Single	5 (38.5)	8 (61.5)	0.001	4 (30.8)	9 (69.2)	0.174	3 (23.1)	10 (76.9)	<0.001	5 (38.5)	8 (61.5)	0.913
Married	66 (19.3)	267 (80.7)		112 (32.7)	230 (67.3)		69 (20.2)	273 (79.8)		150 (43.8)	192 (56.2)	
Widowed	19 (42.2)	26 (57.8)		21 (46.7)	24 (53.3)		22 (47.9)	23 (52.1)		19 (42.2)	26 (57.8)	
Morbidity												
DM2	27 (26.7)	74 (73.3)	0.022	36 (35.6)	65 (64.4)	<0.001	26 (25.7)	75 (74.3)	0.059	57 (56.4)	43 (43.6)	<0.001
HTN	28 (28)	72 (72)		53 (53)	47 (47)		22 (22)	78 (78)		55 (55)	45 (45)	
Asthma	19 (25.3)	56 (74.7)		28 (37.3)	47 (62.7)		25 (33.3)	50 (66.7)		34 (45.3)	41 (54.7)	
CVD	16 (12.9)	108 (87.1)		20 (16.1)	104 (83.9)		21 (16.9)	103 (83.1)		28 (22.6)	96 (77.4)	
Duration (yrs.)												
< 2	11 (30.5)	8 (69.5)	<0.001	18 (50)	18 (50)	0.059	9 (25)	27 (75)	0.507	19 (52.8)	17 (47.2)	0.336
2 - 5	49 (33.3)	98 (66.7)		43 (29.2)	104 (70.8)		38 (25.8)	109 (74.2)		59 (39.5)	89 (60.5)	
> 5	30 (13.8)	187 (86.2)		76 (35)	141 (65)		47 (21.6)	170 (78.4)		97 (44.7)	120 (55.3)	

Satisfaction side effect information is associated with morbidity ($P < 0.001$), education ($P < 0.001$), marital status ($P = 0.019$), duration of therapy ($P < 0.001$) and age ($P = 0.014$) (**Table 5**).

Table 5: Satisfaction with information on medicine side effect(s)

Variable	Q9. How to get further supply			Q10. Whether your medicine have unwanted side effects			Q11. What are your risks of getting side effects			Q12. What do you do when you experience side effects		
	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value
Gender												
Male	102 (47.1)	115 (52.9)	0.272	78 (35.9)	139 (64.1)	0.173	68 (36.3)	149 (63.7)	0.135	70 (32.2)	147 (67.8)	<0.001*
Female	76 (41.5)	107 (58.5)		54 (29.5)	129 (70.5)		45 (24.6)	138 (75.4)		31 (16.9)	152 (83.1)	
Age (yrs.)												
≤ 40	47 (51.1)	45 (48.9)	0.226	23 (25)	69 (75)	0.016*	29 (31.5)	63 (68.5)	0.204	16 (17.4)	76 (82.6)	0.014*
41 – 50	41 (41)	59 (59)		42 (42)	58 (58)		34 (34)	66 (66)		29 (29)	71 (71)	
51 – 60	38 (48.1)	41 (51.9)		33 (47.8)	46 (52.2)		23 (29.1)	56 (70.9)		18 (22.8)	61 (77.2)	
61 – 70	32 (46.4)	37 (53.6)		20 (28.9)	49 (71.1)		16 (23.2)	53 (76.8)		27 (39.1)	42 (60.9)	
≥71	20 (33.3)	40 (66.7)		14 (23.3)	46 (76.7)		11 (18.3)	49 (81.7)		11 (18.3)	49 (81.7)	
Education												
Primary	47 (50.5)	56 (49.5)	0.019*	25 (26.9)	68 (73.1)	0.064	13 (14.1)	80 (85.9)	<0.001*	12 (12.9)	81 (87.1)	<0.001*
Secondary	98 (49)	112 (51)		77 (38.5)	123 (61.5)		39 (19.5)	161 (80.5)		26 (13)	174 (87)	
Tertiary	33 (30.8)	74 (69.2)		30 (28)	77 (72)		61 (57)	46 (43)		63 (58.9)	44 (41.1)	
Marital status												
Single	8 (61.5)	4 (38.5)	0.028*	7 (53.8)	6 (46.2)	0.739	8 (61.5)	5 (38.5)	0.019*	7 (53.8)	6 (46.2)	0.051
Married	153 (30.1)	189 (69.9)		112 (32.7)	240 (67.3)		92 (26.9)	260 (73.1)		82 (23.9)	260 (76.1)	
Widowed	17 (37.8)	40 (62.2)		13 (28.9)	22 (71.1)		13 (28.9)	32 (71.1)		12 (26.7)	33 (73.3)	
Morbidity												
DM2	49 (48.5)	52 (51.5)	<0.001*	39 (38.6)	62 (61.4)	<0.001*	36 (35.6)	65 (64.4)	<0.001*	41 (44.5)	60 (55.5)	<0.001*
HTN	54 (54)	46 (46)		48 (48)	52 (52)		39 (39)	61 (61)		35 (35)	65 (65)	
Asthma	41 (54.7)	34 (45.3)		25 (33.3)	50 (66.7)		26 (34.7)	49 (65.3)		14 (18.7)	61 (81.3)	
CVD	34 (27.4)	90 (72.6)		20 (16.1)	104 (83.9)		12 (9.7)	112 (90.3)		11 (8.9)	113 (91.1)	
Duration (yrs.)												
< 2	17 (47.2)	19 (52.8)	0.412	13 (36.1)	23 (63.9)	<0.001*	9 (25)	27 (75)	0.877	13 (36.1)	23 (63.9)	<0.001*
2 - 5	71 (48.3)	76 (51.7)		65 (44.2)	82 (55.8)		43 (29.2)	104 (70.8)		56 (38.1)	91 (61.9)	
> 5	90 (41.5)	127 (58.5)		54 (24.9)	163 (75.1)		61 (28.1)	156 (71.9)		32 (14.7)	185 (85.3)	

Satisfaction with information on interactions alcohol, other medicines and sex life is associated with gender (P = 0.009), age (P = 0.011) and morbidity (P<0.001) and education (P<0.001) (**Table 6**).

Table 6: Satisfaction with information on interaction with alcohol and sex life as well as with other medicines

Item	Q13. Whether you may take alcohol while on your medicine			Q14. Whether your medicine interfere with other medicines			Q15. Whether the medicine will make you drowsy			Q16. Whether the medicine will affect your sex life		
	STF (%)	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value	STF	NSTF	P value
Gender												
Male	81 (37.3)	136 (62.7)	0.288	62 (28.6)	155 (71.4)	0.370	58 (26.7)	159 (73.3)	0.164	86 (39.6)	131 (60.4)	0.009
Female	59 (31.7)	124 (68.3)		45 (24.6)	138 (75.4)		38 (20.8)	145 (79.2)		50 (27.3)	133 (72.7)	
Age (yrs.)												
≤ 40	17 (18.4)	75 (81.6)	<0.001	22 (23.9)	70 (76.1)	0.023	26 (28.3)	66 (71.7)	0.032	44 (47.8)	48 (52.2)	0.011
41 – 50	44 (44)	56 (56)		35 (35)	65 (65)		32 (32)	68 (68)		29 (29)	71 (71)	
51 – 60	38 (48.1)	41 (51.9)		24 (30.4)	55 (69.6)		19 (24.1)	60 (75.9)		27 (34.2)	52 (65.8)	
61 – 70	23 (33.3)	46 (66.7)		19 (27.5)	50 (72.5)		10 (14.5)	59 (85.5)		23 (33.3)	46 (66.7)	
≥71	18 (30)	42 (70)		7 (11.7)	53 (88.3)		9 (15)	51 (85)		13 (21.7)	47 (78.3)	
Education												
Primary	22 (23.6)	71 (76.4)	<0.001	14 (15.1)	79 (84.9)	<0.001	9 (9.7)	84 (90.3)	<0.001	26 (27.9)	67 (72.1)	0.297
Secondary	47 (23.5)	153 (76.5)		34 (17)	166 (83)		38 (19)	162 (81)		69 (34.5)	131 (65.5)	
Tertiary	71 (66.3)	36 (33.7)		59 (55.1)	48 (44.9)		49 (45.8)	58 (54.2)		41 (38.3)	66 (61.7)	
Marital status												
Single	5 (38.5)	8 (61.5)	<0.001	4 (30.7)	9 (69.3)	0.092	3 (23.1)	10 (76.9)	0.795	5 (38.5)	8 (61.5)	0.935
Married	105 (30.7)	237 (69.3)		85 (24.8)	257 (75.2)		84 (24.6)	258 (75.4)		116 (33.9)	226 (66.1)	
Widowed	30 (66.7)	15 (33.3)		18 (40)	27 (60)		9 (20)	36 (80)		15 (33.3)	30 (66.7)	
Morbidity												
DM2	48 (47.5)	53 (52.5)	<0.001	44 (43.6)	57 (56.4)	<0.001	30 (29.7)	71 (70.3)	0.011	47 (46.5)	54 (53.5)	<0.001
HTN	29 (29)	71 (71)		31 (31)	69 (69)		32 (32)	68 (68)		36 (36)	64 (64)	
Asthma	35 (46.7)	40 (53.3)		20 (26.7)	55 (73.3)		15 (20)	60 (80)		28 (37.3)	47 (62.7)	
CVD	28 (22.6)	96 (77.4)		12 (9.7)	112 (90.3)		19 (15.3)	105 (84.7)		25 (20.2)	99 (79.8)	
Duration (yrs.)												
< 2	7 (19.4)	29 (80.6)	0.117	14 (38.9)	22 (61.1)	<0.001	10 (27.8)	26 (72.2)	0.001	11 (30.5)	25 (69.5)	0.770
2 - 5	55 (37.4)	92 (62.6)		53 (36.1)	94 (63.9)		49 (33.3)	98 (66.7)		48 (32.6)	99 (67.4)	
> 5	78 (35.9)	139 (64.1)		40 (18.4)	177 (81.6)		37 (17.1)	180 (82.9)		77 (35.5)	140 (64.5)	

The results showed significant association between “*what to do if you forget to take a dose*” and gender (P<0.001), education (P = 0.009), marital status (P<0.001) and duration of therapy (P = 0.003) (**Table 7**).

Table 7: Satisfaction with information on what to do with missed doses

Variable	Q17. What to do if your forget to take a dose		
	STF (%)	NSTF (%)	P value
Gender			
Male	42 (19.3)	175 (80.7)	<0.001
Female	13 (7.1)	170 (92.9)	
Age (yrs.)			
≤ 40	15 (16.3)	77 (83.7)	0.933
41 – 50	14 (14)	86 (86)	
51 – 60	10 (12.6)	69 (87.4)	
61 – 70	9 (13.1)	60 (86.9)	
≥71	7 (11.7)	53 (88.3)	
Educational status			
Primary	11 (11.8)	82 (88.2)	0.009
Secondary	20 (10)	180 (90)	
Tertiary	24 (22.4)	83 (77.6)	
Marital status			
Single	7 (53.8)	6 (46.2)	<0.001
Married	36 (10.5)	306 (89.5)	
Widowed	12 (26.7)	33 (73.3)	
Morbidity			
DM2	17 (16.8)	84 (83.2)	0.082
HTN	19 (19)	81 (81)	
Asthma	9 (12)	66 (88)	
CVD	10 (8.1)	114 (91.9)	
Duration (yrs.)			
< 2	7 (19.4)	29 (80.6)	0.003
2 – 5	30 (20.4)	117 (79.6)	
> 5	18 (8.3)	199 (91.7)	

Key: STF – *satisfied*, NSTF – *not satisfied*

Discussion

Medicine information is an integral part of pharmaceutical card in ambulatory care where it has been demonstrable benefits for patients with chronic diseases. Satisfaction with information is a quality measure from the perspective of patient’s perception of service experience. The results of this study showed that satisfaction was generally poor consistent with some previous studies (Kayyali *et al*, 2016, Cooper *et al*, 2014). There was wide variation in the level satisfaction with different aspects of information as observed in similar studies (Sze *et al*, 2020).

While many patients may also receive medicine information from non-pharmacist sources, it is a core professional responsibility of the pharmacists (Tan *et al*, 2023, Alanazi *et al*, 2018). There is conclusive evidence that pharmacist led medicine information results in with better clinical outcomes (Al Jeraisy *et al*, 2023, Blalock *et al*, 2022). The often contrasting results from satisfaction studies is related to differences in study settings, patients service experience, completeness and relevance of information, method of delivery, complexity and level of health literacy.

Furthermore low satisfaction may be due to uncomfortable items related to culturally sensitivities and those that require patient's knowledge on how medicines work, evidence of efficacy, recognition of side effects and potential interactions. These questions require knowledge of technical details that are too complex to either remember or comprehend for majority of patients. In addition it is known that information provided by other category of health workers tend to be either inadequate and/or incomplete because of deficient knowledge of drug(s) and/or lack of capacity to provide specific medication information (Bowen *et al*, 2017).

Satisfaction with medicine information has been reported to be influenced by multiple factors which vary with study settings and patient sociodemographic variables (Klewitz *et al*, 2019). The result of this study showed significant association between satisfaction and gender, age, morbidity, educational status and duration of therapy which are consistent with previous studies (Sze *et al*, 2020), although contrasting results have also been reported (van Geffen *et al*, 2011, Hussain *et al*, 2013).

The level of education and associated health literacy are known to affect the willingness to ask questions or demand for services particularly on information that carries the risk of social stigma. For instance, patients may sometimes be unwilling to discuss or respond to inquiries related to effect of drugs on sexual performance thereby under reporting such side effects and reluctant to seek further information (Healy *et al*, 2022, Nyblade *et al*, 2019). More challenging is the determination of how much information is adequate, can be easily understood and recall particularly among patients with little

formal education and poor health literacy (Silkane *et al*, 2018, Xu *et al*, 2021).

In addition to these factors, providers sometimes withhold some specific information for fear of discouraging patients from taking their medications (Cooper *et al*, 2014), thereby restricting information to what they think is necessary is necessary (Priebe *et al*, 2019). This has the effect of reducing completeness of information (Showande & Laniyan, 2022), introduce information gaps which will contribute to frustration and dissatisfaction (Rutter & Rutter, 2019). The benefits of satisfaction with medicine information is reported to include positive outcomes of therapy (Watkins *et al*, 2017, Goldstone *et al*, 2021) and better quality of life (Eldooma *et al*, 2023), Several other benefits of adequate medicine information have been reported to include better patient participation, adherence, safety, trust, faster recovery, reduced hospitalization time, better patient cooperation with therapy, higher motivation to follow up appointments and improved feeling of emotional wellbeing (Sertan *et al*, 2023, Bramley *et al*, 2019). These and other benefits are achievable with timely delivery of adequate information tailored to specific needs of patient at various stages of their medical care and medication therapy (Ekadipta *et al*, 2019, Alhassan *et al*, 2022). The near absence of structured medication information in most health facilities in developing countries makes it difficult to measure how well patients are growing in knowledge of medicines and applying the information in self-care. It is therefore attention and resolve structural and administrative barriers that hinder medicine information delivery to patients and other healthcare workers.

Satisfaction with medicine information was generally poor and this raises concerns

about quality of medicine use and delivery system. It is important to consider demographic factors in designing and delivering medicine information to ambulatory patients with chronic diseases.

Strengths and limitations

There was high response rate which contributed to the representativeness of patient population and in addition to the survey being carried out immediately after receiving medications ensured that recall bias minimally affect response. However potential bias may exist with response to

items considered to be socially sensitive in spite of assurances of confidentiality. Furthermore, the study did not distinguish between general experience, new treatment regimen or refill information. The impact of individual drug(s) regimen on satisfaction was not explored which may be a source of limitation to general application of the findings

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References

- Aldarwesh A, Almustanyir A, Alharthi M, Alhayan D (2022). Knowledge of Saudi Patients with Autoimmune Diseases about Hydroxychloroquine Toxicity: The Role of Physician–Patient Communication. *Pharmacy*. 10: 152.
- Adeniyi BA, Ogunleye OO, Erhun WO. (2017). Medicine information satisfaction among patients attending a tertiary care hospital in southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy*, 8(2), 47-52.
- Alanazi A, Al Rabiha F, Gadi H, Househ M, Al Dosari B (2018). Factors influencing pharmacists' intentions to use Pharmacy Information Systems. *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked*. 11: 1 – 8.
- Al Jeraisy M, Alshammari H, Albassam M, Al Aamer K, Abolfotouh MA (2023). Utility of patient information leaflet and perceived impact of its use on medication adherence. *BMC Public Health*. 23: 488.
- Alhassan GN, Bosnak AS, Hamurtekin E (2022). Perceived satisfaction and outcomes from drug information center services provided with a telehealth approach. *Niger Journal of Clinical Practice*. 25: 2053 - 2061.
- Ade A, Debroucher F, Delporte L, De Monclin C, Fayet E, Legendre P, Radoszycki L, Chekroun M (2020). Chronic patients satisfaction and priorities regarding medical care, information and services and quality of life; a French online patient community survey. *BMC Health Services Research*. 20: 511.
- Aggarwal A, Bhasin S, Maheshwari P, Sirivella A, Manogna B, Kaira D, Kumar N, Rekha T, Unnikrishnan B, Mithra P, Holla R (2024). Health literacy and satisfaction regarding medical care among patients attending a tertiary care hospital in Mangalore. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*. 49(Suppl 1): 539.
- Alshahrani F (2023). Involvement of patients in pharmacovigilance. In *Encyclopedia of evidence in Pharmaceutical Public Health and Health Services Research in Pharmacy*, Springer, Cham https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-50247-8_143-1
- Blalock SJ, Solow EB, Reyna VF, Keebler M, Carpenter D, Hunt C, Hickey G, Curtis FR, O’Neil K, Chapman SB (2022). Enhancing patient

- understanding of medication risks and benefits. *Arthritis Care & Research*. 74(1): 142 – 150.
- Bowen JF, Rotz ME, Patterson BJ, Sen S (2017). Nurses' attitudes and behaviors on patient medication education. *Pharmacy Practice (Granada)*. 15(2): 930.
- Benson M, Murphy D, Hall L, Kamp PV, Cook DJ (2021). Medication management for complex patients in primary care: application of a remote asynchronous clinical pharmacist model. *Postgraduate Medicine* 133(7): 784 – 790
- Brouwer AF, Brand PL, van den Berg NJ (2015). Patient education materials on asthma: Are they satisfactory for the patient? *Journal of Asthma*. 52(7): 723-729.
- Boons C, Timmers L, van Schoor NM, Swart EL, Hendrikse NH, Janssen JWM, Hugtenburg JG (2018). Patient satisfaction with information on oral anticancer agent use. *Cancer Medicine*. 7(1): 219–228.
- Bramley D, Innes A, Dass N (2019). Impact of medicines helplines on patient satisfaction, patient outcomes and medicines safety for hospital patients: the development of a rating scale and an evaluation of patients' opinions. *European Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*. 26(6): 301 – 307.
- Bekker CL, Naghani SM, Natsch S, Warternberg NS, van den Bemt BJF (2020). Information needs and patient perceptions of the quality of medication information available in hospitals: a mixed method study. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy*. 42: 1396–1404.
- Cooper JM, Garrett T (2014). Providing medicines information and education to hospital in-patients: patients' experiences and preferences. *Journal of Pharmacy Practice and Research*. 44: 213–219.
- Chan AHY, Aspden T, Brackley K, Ashmore-Price H, Honey M (2020). What information do patients want about their medicines? An exploration of the perspectives of general medicine inpatients. *BMC Health Services Research*. 20:1131.
- Donaldson LJ, Kelley ET, Dhingra-Kumar N, Kienny M-P, Sheikh A (2017). Medication without harm: WHO's Third Global Patient Safety Challenge. *The Lancet*. 389(10080):1680–1681.
- Devi R, Kanitkar K, Narendhar R, Sehmi K, Subramaniam K (2020). A narrative review of the patient journey through the lens of non-communicable diseases in low and middle income countries. *Advances in Therapeutics*. 37(12): 4808 – 4830.
- Druica E, Ianole-Calin R, Baicus C, Dinescu R (2021). Determinants of satisfaction with services and trust in the information received in community pharmacies: A comparative analysis to foster pharmaceutical care adoption. *Healthcare*. 9: 562.
- Ekadipta KJ (2019). The effect of the quality of drug information service on patient's satisfaction level in BJPJS out-patient installation of Siloam hospital Kebon Jeruk. *International Journal of Applied Science*. 3(1): 18 – 29.
- Eldooma I, Maatoug M, Yousif M (2023). Outcomes of pharmacist-led pharmaceutical care interventions within community pharmacies: Narrative review. *Integrated Pharmacy Research and Practice*. 12: 113–126.
- Eibergen L, Janssen MJA, Blom L, Karapinar-Carkit F (2018). Informational needs and recall of in-hospital medication changes of recently discharged patients. *Research in Social Administrative Pharmacy*. 14(2): 146–152.
- Geryk LL, Blalock S, DeVellis RF, Morella K, Carpenter DM (2016). Associations between patient characteristics and the amount of arthritis medication information

- patients receive. *Journal of Health Communication*. 21(10): 1122–1130.
- Goldstone LW, DiPaula BA, Werremeyer A, Botts S, Hepburn B, Liu HY, Duckworth K, Young AS, Kelly DL (2021). The role of board-certified psychiatric pharmacists in expanding access to care and improving patient outcomes. *Psychiatry Services*. 72(7):794–801.
- Hussain S, Hussain AAS, Hussain K, Asif MA, Khalil MM, Rahman DA, Charara R, Alsuwaidi S, AlKhani R (2013). Pharmacist–patient counselling in Dubai: assessment and reflection on patient satisfaction. *European Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*. 20: 241–247
- Horne R, Hankins M, Jenkins R (2001). The satisfaction with information about medicines scale (SIMS): a new measurement tool for audit and research. *Quality Health Care*. 10: 135–140.
- Hammar T, Zetterholm M (2020). Patients views on information about medications- a pharmacy-based survey focusing on their information sources and experiences of pharmacists using a clinical decision support system. *Proceedings of the 18th International Symposium on Health Information management Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.15626/ishimr.2020.15>
- Healy M, Richard A, Kidia K (2022). How to reduce stigma and bias in clinical communication; a narrative review. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*. 37(10): 2533 – 2540.
- Idris IO, Oguntade AS, Mensah EA, Kitamura N (2020). Prevalence of non-communicable diseases and its risk factors among Ijegan-Isheri Osun residents in Lagos State, Nigeria: a community based cross sectional study. *BMC Public Health*. 20: 1258.
- Johnson A, Sandford J, Tyndall J (2003). Written and verbal information versus verbal information only for patients being discharged from acute hospital settings to home. *Cochrane Databased of Systematic Reviews*. 4: CD003716.
- Jose J (2020). Communication on drug safety-related matters to patients: is it even more significant in this digital era? *Therapeutic Advances in Drug Safety*. 11: 1–4.
- Kayyali R, Gomes AM, Mason T, Naik M (2016). Patient’s perceptions of medication counselling from community pharmacies. *Pharmacy and Pharmacology International Journal*. 4(2): 334 - 337
- Klewitz F, Nöhre M, Bauer-Hohmann M, Tegtbur U, Schiffer L, Pape L, Schiffer M, de Zwaan M (2019). Information needs of patients about immunosuppressive medication in a German kidney transplant sample: prevalence and correlates. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. 10: 444.
- Kusch MK, Haefeli WE, Seidling HM (2018). How to meet patients’ individual needs for drug information - a scoping review. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 12:2339–2555.
- Langst G, Seidling HM, Stützle M, Ose D, Baudendistel I, Szecsenyi J, Wensing M, Mahler C (2015). Factors associated with medication information in diabetes care: differences in perceptions between patients and health care professionals. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 9: 1431–1441.
- Lorber M, Reljic NM, Kegl B, Fekonja Z, Stiglic G, Davey A, Kmetec S (2024). Person-centred care; Support strategy for managing non communicable diseases. *Healthcare*. 12(5): 526.
- Lucca JM, Kurdi S, Albaqshi B, Joseph R (2022). Patient satisfaction with pharmaceutical care services for chronic diseases and their medication adherence during COVID-19 in

- Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice*. 30(2): 136 – 142.
- Makhinova T, Barner JC, Brown CM, Richards KM, Rascati KL, Nag A (2022). Improving asthma management: patient–pharmacist partnership program in enhancing therapy adherence. *Pharmacy*. 10: 34.
- Martin RW (2019). The impact of health literacy on rating of healthcare experience. *MUSC Theses and Dissertations*. 221. <http://medica-musc.researchcommons.org/theses/221>
- Nyblade L, Stockton MA, Wouters E, Giger K, Bond V, Ekstrand ML, McLean R, Mitchell EMH, Nelson LRE, Sapag JC, Siraprapasiri T, Turan J, Wouters E (2019). Stigma in health facilities: Why it matters and how we can change it. *BMC Medicine*. 17: 25.
- Nafradi L, Galimberti E, Nakamoto K, Schulz PJ (2016). Intentional and unintentional medication non-adherence in hypertension: the role of health literacy, empowerment and medication beliefs. *Journal of Public Health Research*. 5(3): 762.
- Nguyen TM, La Caze A, Cottrell N. (2019). What are validated self-report adherence scales really measuring? A systematic review. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 85(10): 2066-2077.
- Niriayo YL, Kumela K, Kassa TD, Angamo MT (2018). Drug therapy problems and contributing factors in the management of heart failure patients in Jimma University specialized hospital, Southwest Ethiopia. *Plos One*. 13(10): e0206120.
- Newman TV, San-Juan-Rodriguez A, Parekh N, Swart ECS, Klein-Fedyshin M, Shrank WH, Hernandez I (2020). Impact of community pharmacist-led interventions in chronic disease management on clinical, utilization, and economic outcomes: an umbrella review. *Research in Social Administrative Pharmacy*. 16(9):1155–1165
- Ofilo SC, Okenwa SC, Iyi CL, Ekweo-zor CA, Uwaezuoke C, Onuzulike IJ, Somtochukwu MR, Igbokwe J, Odo CL (2023). Assessment of patients' satisfaction with pharmaceutical care services in a Nigerian teaching hospital: A cross sectional study. *Journal of Advances in Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 25 (100340): 1-10.
- Priebe S, Conneely M McCabe R, Bird V (2019). What can clinicians do to improve outcomes across psychiatric treatments: a conceptual review of non-specific components. *Epidemiology in Psychiatric Science*. 29: e48.
- Rutter J, Rutter P (2019). Impact of pharmacy medicine information service advice on clinician and patient outcomes: an overview. *Health Information & Libraries Journal*. 36: 299–317.
- Rameshkumar T, Haputhanthrige IU1, Misbahunnisa MY, Galappaththy P (2022). Patients' knowledge about medicines improves when provided with written compared to verbal information in their native language. *Plos One*. 17(10): e0274901.
- Sheikh A, Dhingra-Kumar N, Kelley E, Kieny MP, Donaldson LJ (2017). The third global patient safety challenge: tackling medication-related harm. *Bulletin of World Health Organization*. 95(8): 546–546A
- Sze WT, Pudney R, Wei L (2020). Inpatients' satisfaction towards information received about medicines. *European Journal Hospital Pharmacy*. 27: 280–285.
- Showande SJ, Laniyan MW (2022). Patient medication counselling in community pharmacy: evaluation of the quality and content. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice*. 15: 103.
- Sertan A, Cek K, Oniz A, Ozgoren M (2023). The influence of medicine approaches on patient trust,

- satisfaction, and loyalty. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 11(9): 1254.
- Silkane V, Davidsons A, Veliverronena (2018). The role of health literacy in predicting patient satisfaction with healthcare. *Society Integration education. Proceedings of the international Scientific Conference, Volume VII, May 25th – 26th, 2018, 240 – 250.* <https://doi.org/10.17770/sie2018vol1.3223>
- Sulistyaningrum IH, Pribadi P, Santoso A, Arfianto E, Pangestuti RCA, Umma N, Ningrum MP (2023). The complex mechanism of developing trust in pharmacy. *Pharmacia*. 70(3): 765 – 770.
- Tan, YXF, Liim STL, Lim JL, Ng TTM, Chng HT (2023). Drug information-seeking behaviours of physicians, nurses and pharmacists: A systematic literature review. *Health information and Library Journal*. 40(2): 125–168.
- Takaki H, Abe T, Hagihara A (2017). Physicians' and pharmacists' information provision and patients' psychological distress. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*. 31(5): 575–582.
- Undeberg MR, McKeirnan KC, Easley D (2022). Respecting the patient's Choice: A case of possible drug-induced Parkinsonism. *Pharmacy*. 10: 10.
- Unni E, Bae S (2022). Exploring a new theoretical model to explain the behavior of medication adherence. *Pharmacy*. 10: 43.
- van Geffen EC, Philbert D, van Boheemen C, van Dijk L, Bos MB, Bouvy ML (2011). Patients' satisfaction with information and experiences with counseling on cardiovascular medication received at the pharmacy. *Patient Education and Counselling*. 83(3): 303–309.
- Walker RE, Nelson LA, Kriz C, Iuppa CA, Liu Y, Diefenderfer LA, Elliott ESR, Sommi RW (2023). Enhancing outcomes: acceptability of medication formulations for the treatment of acute agitation in a psychiatric population. *Pharmacy*. 11: 4.
- Watkins A, McKee J, Hughes C, Pfeifferberger T (2017). Community pharmacists' attitudes toward providing care and services to patients with severe and persistent mental illness. *Journal of American Pharmaceutical Association*. 57(3s): S217–S224.
- Wang Y, Wang J (2020). Modelling and prediction of global non communicable diseases. *BMC Public Health*. 20: 822.
- Wongtaweeekij Km Corlett S, Krska J, Pongwecharak J, Jarensirijpornkul N (2021). Patient's experiences and perspectives of receiving written medicine information about medicines: A qualitative study. *Patient Preferences and Adherence*. 15: 569 – 580.
- Xu RH, Zhou LM, Wong ELY, Wang D (2021). The association between patient's eHealth literacy and satisfaction with shared decision making and wellbeing: Multi-centre cross sectional study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. 23(9): e26721